

Molecular Weights and Shapes of Synthetic Humic Acids: Diffusion Study

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The sodium salts of the synthetic humic acids prepared from glucose, catechol and hydroquinone have been subjected to diffusion study. From this study, the molecular weights of these synthetic preparations have been determined. The humic acids show a coiled configuration in a medium of high ionic strength, which can reasonably be approximated by rigid spherical or ellipsoidal models.

A great variety of molecular weights for natural humic acids have been reported. In view of the great heterogeneity of humic acids Scheffer, Welte and Ziechmann¹ prefer the term 'particle weight' to molecular weight. The reported values of molecular weights of synthetic humic acid preparations are also varied, though to a much smaller degree. Welte¹, failing to observe any sedimentation pattern at 200,000 g. assigned 10,000 as the upper limit for molecular weights of synthetic humic acids and finally considered them to be markedly polydisperse and probably spherical in shape. Scheffer, Welte and Ziechmann¹ also compared a number of methods for estimating molecular weights of synthetic humic acids and obtained a 'particle weight' of about 1,000 from melting point depression in urea, 400-600 from micro-method of distillation of Banger¹, and 700-800 from viscosity measurements. Employing diffusion technique of Northrup and Anson² with a special modification developed by Welte¹, they further obtained 600-800 as the particle weight. They used the same technique of steady state diffusion introducing certain refinements and modifications³⁻⁵. Then from the measured apparent diffusion coefficients at different concentrations, true or differential diffusion coefficient was calculated, following the procedure outlined by Gordon⁷ and extended by Stokes⁶. The latter when extrapolated to zero concentration gives D^0 which is related to the frictional coefficient and molecular weight as follows :

$$f = \frac{kT}{D^0} = 6\pi\eta(f/f_0) \left[\frac{3M(\bar{v}_2 + \delta_1 v_1^0)}{4\pi N} \right]^{1/3} \quad \dots (1)$$

where f = actual frictional coefficient of the particle and $f_0 = 6\pi\eta R_0$ is the frictional coefficient of a solvated spherical particle of radius R_0 . f/f_0 and δ_1 represent respectively asymmetry of the hydrodynamic entity and the solvation in gm/gm of the

material in solution. By setting $f/f_0 = 1$ and $\delta_1 = 0$ in eqn. (1), we get

$$f_{mtn} = \frac{kT}{D_{max}^0} = 6\pi\eta \left[\frac{3M\bar{v}_2}{4\pi N} \right]^{1/3} \quad \dots (2)$$

Hence,

$$f/f_{mtn} = \frac{D_{max}^0}{D^0} = f/f_0 \left[\frac{\bar{v}_2 + \delta_1 v_1^0}{\bar{v}_2} \right]^{1/3} \quad \dots (3)$$

The two parameters cannot be evaluated from a single measurement of diffusion coefficient. However, eqn. (3) can, under specified conditions, give us some idea of molecular solvation and asymmetry. First, the difference between the observed value of f/f_{mtn} and the ideal value of 1.0 for unsolvated spheres can be interpreted as due to solvation only, giving the minimum possible value of δ_1 required to produce a sphere with observed diffusion coefficient. The radius of the sphere can then be easily calculated. Secondly, the value of f/f_{mtn} can be ascribed entirely to asymmetry, assigning $\delta_1 = 0$; the magnitude of this asymmetry can then be expressed in term of the axial ratio, a/b , using ellipsoidal model of Perrin⁸.

Scheraga and Mandelkern⁹ have proposed a method for calculating the size and axial ratio of an "effective" hydrodynamic ellipsoid, whose property represents the kinetic unit in solution, without any assumption about the effective molecular volume. For this purpose they utilize the intrinsic viscosity in addition to such experimental data as those of diffusion coefficient. The shape factor, β , introduced by them is given by

$$\beta = \frac{ND[\eta]^{1/3} \cdot M^{1/3} \eta_0}{RT} = \left(\frac{N}{16200\pi^2} \right)^{1/3} (f/f_0) \nu^{1/3} \quad \dots (4)$$

They have prepared tables relating β to the reciprocal of the axial ratio, ρ of the 'effective ellipsoid'. Since β changes negligibly with ρ for flattened ellipsoid, it is possible to distinguish between prolate and oblate models.

The accurate value of molecular weight cannot be obtained from the measurement of D^0 alone. Eqn.

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(4) can be utilised for the estimation of M by assuming the hydrodynamic particles to be spheres, i.e., $\beta = 2.12 \times 10^8$, and by taking the measured value of D and $[\eta]$ in the same solvent. Estimation of M from the combined measurement of D and $[\eta]$ can also be made with the help of eqn. (1), if the value of f/f_0 obtained from viscosity measurement is substituted in it. Longworth¹⁰ has proposed an empirical modification of Stokes' relation,

$$D = a' / (\bar{V}_2^{1/3} - b') \quad \dots (5)$$

where V_2 is the molar volume of the solute and $a' = 24.182 \times 10^{-8}$ and $b' = 1.280$ at 25° . So from D_w , 25° the value of \bar{V}_2 is determined and if \bar{v}_2 , the partial specific volume, is known then

$$M = \bar{V}_2 / \bar{v}_2 \quad \dots (6)$$

The parameter R_G , the radius of gyration is often used to characterise macromolecules of different configurational types. For solid spheres R_G is related¹¹ to the Radius R_e of the sphere by

$$R_G^2 = 3/5 R_e^2 \quad \dots (7)$$

If the molecule is a flexible coil the following relation holds¹¹,

$$[\eta] = \frac{10\pi N}{3M} \xi^3 R_G^3 \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\text{with } \xi = 0.875$$

$$D^0 = \frac{kT}{6\pi\eta\xi_f R_G} \quad \dots (9)$$

$$\text{with } \xi_f = 0.665$$

where the parameters possess the meaning usually attached to them. There is some question about the value of the parameters ξ and ξ_f but the resulting uncertainty is only about 10%, ξ_f according to the best quantitative theory¹² is a universal constant equal to 0.665.

Materials and Methods

The diffusion coefficient of the different artificially prepared sodium salts of the humic acids¹³ was determined in 0.25 M NaCl by means of Northrup and Anson's method², using three cells approximately 15 ml, 20 ml and 35 ml and with G_4 base. Both the solvent (0.25 M NaCl soln.) and solution were out-gassed prior to use. Diffusion was allowed to proceed for 24-30 hr following a primary diffusion for 20-24 hr. The thermostat was maintained at $35^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$. The volume of the inner and outer solutions were kept the same while calibrating the cell and in subsequent measurements. The calibration curve was made for each sample by plotting optical density at 470 nm against known concentrations in the region where linearity was followed. The calibration of the cells was done with 0.1 M KCl diffusing into water at 25° and using the value $1.838 \times 10^{-5} \text{cm}^2 \text{sec}^{-1}$

given by Gordon⁷ for the diffusion coefficient of KCl, since diffusion proceeded for a comparatively short time.

Partial Specific Volume

The partial specific vol, \bar{v}_2 , was determined from pycnometric measurements of the sodium humate solutions both in aqueous and in 0.25 M NaCl solution, at $35^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$. Driicker's¹⁴ equation was used

for the calculation of $v_s - v_0$, namely, $v_s - v_0 = \frac{\gamma - r}{1 + r}$,

where v = vol. of the soln. containing γ gm of solute and 1 gm of solvent, v_0 = sp. vol. of the solvent and $r = m/m_0$, m and m_0 being the corrected weights of the solution and solvent respectively in the pycnometer. Plotting $v_s - v_0$ against r gives the partial specific volume of the solute molecules, since

$$\bar{v}_2 = \frac{\delta(v_s - v_0)}{\delta r} \quad \text{The results are shown in Table 1.}$$

TABLE 1

System	$D^0_{0.25M, 35^\circ}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{sec}^{-1} \times 10^6$)	Partial sp. vol. \bar{v}_2 in		$[\eta]$ in ml/g. in	
		Water	0.25M NaCl	0.1M NaCl (Expt.)	0.25M NaCl (Fuoss plot)
HQ-Na	4.22	0.42	0.44	4.5	3.8
CT-Na	4.35	0.56	0.58	3.5	3.1
GL-Na	4.80	0.60	0.53	3.6	3.0

Viscosity :

The intrinsic viscosities $[\eta]$ of Na-humate solutions are given in Table 1. The details of viscosity measurements for the purpose of evaluating $[\eta]$ have been reported elsewhere¹³. The intrinsic viscosities in 0.25 M NaCl solution are obtained from Fuoss plot¹⁵.

Results and Discussion

The calculated values of differential diffusion coefficients are given in Table 1. From these D^0 values the molecular weights were estimated according to the procedure mentioned above. When ever β is involved, $[\eta]$ 0.25 M NaCl was combined with D^0 0.25 M, 35° . In using eqn. (1) f/f_0 obtained from $[\eta]$ 0.25 M NaCl and D^0 0.25 M NaCl were combined. Similarly, f/f_0 from the measured value of $[\eta]$ 0.1M NaCl was combined with D^0 0.1M NaCl obtained from the relation

$$D^0_{0.25M NaCl} \times \eta_{0.25M NaCl} = D^0_{0.1M NaCl} \times \eta_{0.1M NaCl}$$

In order to calculate \bar{V}_2 from Longworth's equation D_w^0 , 25° was calculated from the relation

$$D^0_{w, 25^\circ} = D^0_{0.25M, 35^\circ} \left(\frac{298 \times \eta_{0.25M}}{308 \times \eta_w} \right)$$

The results of calculation are shown in Table 2, from which it will be seen that the molecular weights

TABLE 2. MOLECULAR WEIGHT APPROXIMATION

System	Eqn. (5)	Scheraga and Mandelkern parameter β (Eqn. 4)		From Eqn. (1)	
	$D_{w,25}^0 = \frac{a'}{v_2^{1/3} - b'}$ ($a' = 24.182 \times 10^{-6}$ $b' = 1.28$)	using $D_{0.1M, 35}^0$ and $[\eta]_{0.1M, 35}^0$	using $D_{0.25M}^0$ and $[\eta]_{0.25M}$	using f/f_0 from $[\eta]_{0.1M}$ $D_{0.1M}^0$	using f/f_0 from $[\eta]_{0.25M}$ & $D_{0.25}^0$
HQ-Na	834	530	629	726	830 (2.33)**
CT-Na	583	623	700	689	795 (2.21)
GL-Na	427	450	531	616	628 (2.24)

TABLE 3. SOLVATION/ASYMMETRY CALCULATIONS FROM DIFFUSION DATA

System	Maximum solvation $f/f_0 = 1$		Maximum asymmetry $\delta_1 = 0; f/f_0 = f/f_{min}$			Compromise calculation $\delta_1 = 0.1$		
	δ_1 (gm/gm)	Re (Å)	f/f_{min} $= f/f_0$	a/b (P.E.)*	a/b (O.E.)	f/f_0	a/b (P.R.)	a/b (P.E.)
HQ-Na	0.18	7.20	1.409	6.28	7.90	1.149	3.55	3.56
CT-Na	0.17	6.99	1.265	4.09	4.86	1.079	2.63	2.63
GL-Na	0.14	6.33	1.275	4.19	5.02	1.074	2.49	2.50

* P.E. = Prolate ellipsoid; O.E. = oblate ellipsoid.

TABLE 4. SOLVATION/ASYMMETRY CALCULATIONS FROM VISCOSITY DATA

System	Maximum solvation ($\nu = 2.5$)		Maximum asymmetry $\delta_1 = 0$			Compromise calculation ($\delta_1 = 0.1$)		
	δ_1 (g/g)	Re (Å)	f/f_{min} $= f/f_0$	a/b (P.E.)	a/b (O.E.)	f/f_0	a/b (P.E.)	a/b (O.E.)
HQ-Na	1.08	7.93	8.63	6.90	10.6	7.04	5.8	8.3
CT-Na	0.67	7.30	5.37	4.40	5.7	4.58	3.6	4.8
GL-Na	0.69	6.72	5.72	4.65	6.2	4.82	3.8	4.8

of the humic acid salts range from 450 to 800, in good agreement with those obtained by Scheffer, Welte and Ziechmann¹ for similar synthetic humic acids.

Molecular Shapes :

The maximum solvation and asymmetry were then calculated using the assigned value of M as given in column 6 of Table 2. It is unlikely that humic acid particles are either perfect spheres or are unsolvated. Compromise calculation has, therefore, been done assuming a certain degree of hydration ($\delta_1 = 0.1$ g/g) and some asymmetry i.e., for a particular axial ratio of the ellipsoids. It would be noted, of course, that the overall shape of humic acid particles may be quite irregular, but ellipsoids of revolution are assumed because this is the only model for which equations are available and by means of which f/f_0 may be interpreted. It is, however, justified to treat a randomly coiled flexible polymer as an equivalent sphere. Similar information can also be obtained from $[\eta]_{0.25M}$ by using graphical relation given by Simha¹⁶ between f/f_{min} and a/b . The results are given in the Tables 3 and 4.

The maximum values of solvation obtained in the two different approaches, diffusion and viscosity, are widely different though the radii of corresponding hydrodynamic spheres agree fairly closely. The

discrepancy between these two hydrodynamical studies is not appreciably decreased by considering a reasonable but equal degree of hydration ($\delta_1 = 0.1$ gm)

Fig. 1. Diffusion curves of hydroquinone humic acid

X : $-\bar{D}$ vs \sqrt{C} , Y : $-\bar{D}^0(\bar{C}_B)$ vs $\sqrt{\bar{C}_B}$, Z : $-D$ vs O (upper absciss). ● Theoretical points calculated from graph Y.

as is reflected in the difference in the computed axial ratios, particularly in the case of hydroquinone

TABLE 5. RADII OF GYRATION

Molecular Model	HQ-Na	CT-Na	GL-Na
	R_G A	R_G A	R_G A
Assuming sphere R_e from viscosity data (Table 3) (cf. eqn. 6)	10.2	9.45	8.67
Assuming random coil From D^0 (cf. eqn. 8) $f = 0.665$	10.8	10.5	9.52
From 0.25M (cf. eqn. 7) $= 0.875$	9.07	8.37	7.68

humic acid. It is evident, however, that if a correlation is wanted, the oblate ellipsoidal model for catechol humic acid and glucose humic acid is

Fig. 2. Diffusion curves of catechol humic acid ($S_2O_3^{2-}$)

X : \bar{D} vs \sqrt{C} , Y : $\bar{D}^0(\bar{C}_B)$ vs $\sqrt{\bar{C}_B}$, Z : \bar{D} vs C (upper absciss.) ● Theoretical points calculated from graph Y.

Fig. 3. Diffusion curves for glucose humate

X : \bar{D} vs \sqrt{C} , Y : $\bar{D}^0(\bar{C}_B)$ vs $\sqrt{\bar{C}_B}$, Z : \bar{D} vs C (upper absciss.) ● Theoretical points calculated from graph Y.

completely ruled out, though the prolate model gives axial ratios in the two different approaches quite in agreement with each other, within the limits of error involved in the present investigation. In the case of hydroquinone humic acid it can be shown that not equal amount but some degree (30% of the maximum) of hydration would give corroborating axial ratio for the prolate model in the two different approaches. The maximum asymmetry observed in diffusion study gives axial ratios for prolate ellipsoids, which, within the experimental error, agree fairly closely with the corresponding values calculated from viscosity measurements. This agreement, as well as the discrepancy when solvation is taken into consideration, appears to indicate that the humate particles can be approximated as rigid and almost, if not fully, hydrated prolate ellipsoids of revolution. Although this sort of discrepancy has been observed in other systems, "e.g., fibrinogen", nevertheless the comparison of parameters calculated from diffusion measurements with those from viscosity should not be stressed too far, considering the limitations of Fuoss plot for evaluating $[\eta]_{0.25M}$. An alternative approach without assuming rigidity or hydration is due to Scheraga and Mandelkern⁹. While the agreement between the values of molecular weights obtained from Longworth's relation (eqn. 5) and with Scheraga and Mandelkern parameter $\beta = 2.12 \times 10^6$ (eqn. 4) in the case of catechol humic and glucose humic acid salts (Table 2) indicate a spherical or oblate ellipsoidal model, the wide difference in the case of hydroquinone humic acid rules out this possibility. However, this comparison is subject to the validity of Longworth's empirical relations as well as of equations (9) and (10). A second value of molecular weight is given in column 4 of Table 2, which refers to D^0 and $[\eta]$ at 0.25 M NaCl. It is also limited by the accuracy of evaluating $[\eta]_{0.25M}$ from the Fuoss plot. Columns 5 and 6 of Table 2 show the molecular weights calculated from eqn. (1). They are also subject to the validity and accuracy of the Fuoss plot, but show fairly reasonable values

which compare well with those given in the same Table. The shape factor, β , corresponding to the molecular weights shown in column 6 are given in column 7. The corresponding axial ratios favour the prolate ellipsoidal model for these particles. Results involving β should, however, be interpreted with caution since very accurate measurements under identical conditions of the quantities concerned are required to calculate β . Moreover, as Tanford and Buzzel¹⁷ showed, the theory might be inapplicable to particles which are not rigid ellipsoids.

In order to decide whether the hydrodynamic particles are spherical or nearly so in shape, or are randomly coiled chains, the radii of gyration have been computed from the equations (6), (7) and (8). But since light scattering measurements were not possible with the humic acids, the usual comparison with them could not be made. Nevertheless, the values of radii of gyration indicate that the humate particles may be flexible coils giving the kinetic entity the shape of an equivalent sphere in a medium of high ionic strength. This type of calculation of radii of gyration may be criticised in view of the low molecular weights of the humic acids, since in that case ξ_f as assumed, will not remain constant. These comparatively smaller humic acid molecules, though expected to be somewhat stiff, show a contractile nature indicating a reasonable degree of flexibility. Moreover, they show a coiled configuration in a

medium of high ionic strength, which can reasonably be approximated by rigid, spherical or ellipsoidal models.

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